

ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY

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Abstract: This article provides a comparative study of the interrelationships and differences between the phraseological units of the Uzbek and English languages, as well as the forms of their translation.

Keywords: phraseology, synonymy of phraseological units, antonymy, idiom, proverb.

Today's linguistics places a strong emphasis on phraseology. This field has lately grown, and several scientific studies are being done in it.

The study of phrases is called phraseology. The study of phrases and word associations in terms of their structure and meaning is known as phraseology. A phraseological unit is a speech-related unit that consists of multiple separate lexemes.

It is a metaphorical spiritual combination that takes the shape of Tepa Sochi standing up and reaching for the sky, displaying the appropriate plumage, and playing the first fiddle. Phraseological expressions exist in many languages, although they are particularly prevalent in English. They are thought to be a product of national wisdom. With English

Scientists categorize phraseological compounds into three major classes based on their origin:

1. Outdated English phraseological combinations
2. Phrases that have been combined from several languages
3. Word groups from the Americanized form of the English language

Old traditions, historical facts, and practices of the English people that are directly tied to The traditions of the English people are expressed in many phraseological combinations, and faith reflects both known and unknown historical truths about English history.

A significant contribution to enrichment was made by William Shakespeare's English lexicon. The only thing the Bible is second to in terms of phraseologisms is what he invented. Let's examine a few of them now:

Cakes and ale: cake and beer; carefree joy; living life to the fullest.

"A fool's paradise" is a world of imagination and delight.

Confession to the enemy is a way to pay the devil back.

The green-eyed monster is a green-eyed, vile, and envious individual.

Have an itchy palm—to bribe; avaricious

To lavishly praise someone, use the expression "lay it on with a trowel."

not giving a damn and treating everyone equally.

He's there thanks to action-search.

Be wise—a deer is there!

I'm tired of it, and you touched my spirit! Enough!

to try, to give it a shot.

Shakespeare is just one of several English authors whose lexicon has been expanded. They include Walter Scott, Edmond Spencer, Thomas Browne, Geoffrey Chaucer, and others.

Unknown authors are responsible for the phraseology that describes conventions, traditions, and beliefs; it was developed over time among the populace. This terminology

Unions are illustrations of people's inventiveness.

They are obtained through linguistic equivalents rather than a direct translation from one language to another. The reason for this is that while each country's traditions are unique, so are its conventions, values, and traditions. For instance: take a huge bite of bread; put up with work that is not enough; try in vain; too much entanglement will show the waist; bite off more than one can chew; Have a bee in one's bonnet and keep one's head high while thinking a lot. Attending a dance for someone means running for them, being at their service all the while, and running for the unfortunate competitor.

The announcement followed the words that kicked off the tournament.

A. Mamatov, an Uzbek linguist who has studied the field of phraseology, categorizes phraseological combinations into four groups based on how they are formed:

1. Phraseologisms formed in terms of connection with personal activity and psyche:

to be open-minded, to be disappointed, to fall blue when hitting the ground, etc.

2. Phraseologisms formed depending on the profession: like a busker's shuttle

3. Phraseologisms formed on the basis of images characteristic of animals: His leg is burned.

like a chicken, like my aunt's calf, a fed lamb, etc.

4. Phraseologisms formed in terms of religion: God bless the prophet

like standing with a cane.

Similar to the Uzbek language, English contains several idioms and expressions that are borrowed from other languages. Many idioms, especially from the French and Latin languages, are well-versed. There were also others who arrived who spoke Greek, Spanish, Italian, and many other languages.

Combinations of phrases that are well-rehearsed convey bookishness.

Additionally, phraseological combinations are assimilated in a variety of ways: word-for-word acquisition, for instance, conjure: somewhat modified, with a part changed and a part translated (a propos (or apropos) of nothing

From nothing to nothing, there is nothing (nothing from something). There are numerous phrasal units that have direct correspondences and are literally rendered the same way in Uzbek and English.

occurs. To play with fire, for instance, first ponder before speaking, as in think first, then say.

Proverbs can be used interchangeably:

Make hay while the sun shines. Strike

the iron while it is hot.

After rain comes sunshine; the sun comes out after the rain.

A bird may be known by its song.

A honey tongue and a heart of gull

A word spoken is past recalling.

After the doctor's death, after the wedding drum

As you brew, so you must drink.

In conclusion, every language is vibrant and full of rich idioms. When we use it regularly, our speech becomes more elegant and fluid. As you can see from the examination of

phraseological combinations above, phraseology should be studied as a separate discipline rather than as a subfield of linguistics.

When translating phraseological units in speech from one language to another, particular care must be taken to ensure proper application. These units are for creative or spoken text.

The number of options is determined by a linguistic dictionary, in addition to offering emotional expression and visuals.

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